

Globalization Enables Telkom Indonesia to be Interconnected with International Telecommunications Networks, Supporting Seamless Communication and Data Exchange Across Border

Muhammad Asif Khan

Faculty of Economic and Business Bhayangkara University

Corresponding Author: Muhammad Asif Khan Baristerasi@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Telkom Indonesia, International Expansion, Cultural Adaptability, Globalization, Digital Innovations

Received : 22, October

Revised : 21, November

Accepted: 30, December

©2022 Khan: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This case study delves into the globalization journey of Telkom Indonesia, a leading telecommunications company in Southeast Asia. The case study explores Telkom Indonesia's motivations for embracing globalization, the challenges encountered, and the resultant impact on the company's growth and global connectivity. It then delves into the company's decision to venture beyond national borders, exploring the drivers behind its international expansion, such as seeking new growth opportunities, accessing untapped markets, and diversifying revenue streams. It also assesses how Telkom Indonesia's interconnected telecommunications networks support seamless communication and data exchange across borders, enabling the company to serve an increasingly diverse and global customer base. Challenges faced during the globalization process are explored, including regulatory complexities, cultural differences, and competition from international telecom giants. The study highlights the importance of cultural sensitivity and adaptability as Telkom Indonesia navigates varying legal environments and customer preferences in international markets. The study evaluates the company's approach to tailoring services and solutions to meet the unique needs and demands of different global markets and emphasizes the transformative impact of globalization on Telkom Indonesia's growth and global connectivity.

INTRODUCTION

World globalization is a leading factor that leads companies to decide on international expansion with an objective to retain or grow the business. In light of making international marketing strategy decisions, where a company globalizes, the managers meet new challenges that are impacted by deemed cultural and geographic business range. Telkom Indonesia is a good example of companies that have been expanding their businesses internationally since the year 2007, a time when it came up with its subsidiary called Telin. Since, its inception, Telin has expanded to ten more subsidiaries located in more different countries. The primary objective of coming up with the branches was to enhance benefits from their international markets. As a headquarters, Telin was responsible for making the portfolio products together with the key performance indicators (KPIs) for those respective subsidiaries. The Subsidiaries then determine the best program that works in line with the proposed KPIs. However, in some countries where the subsidiaries are located, it is hard to achieve the objectives.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Telkom Indonesia is an Indonesian company within the telecommunications industry. Telkom is one of the telecommunication companies that have an extended history down the line since their inception. Telkom Company is traced as an establishment of the pioneering electromagnetic telegraph service in Indonesia in the year 1856. It was established by the Dutch Colonial Government to connect the Batavia and Buitenzorg states. In the wake of 1884, the Dutch Colonial Government came up with a private company with the objective that the company would provide postal and domestic telegraph services, and later, the company would offer international telegraph services. In 1995, the company became a private company. In the year 2009, the company decided to expand the telecommunication and services in information technology. The company has a mission to be the "The King of Digital in the Region," and its vision is, "Lead Indonesian Digital Innovation and Globalization." Some of the exhibits of the company include opening the data center, Telin and Taisheng collaborating, and the journey footprints the company to be made.

METHODOLOGY

1. The Implications of Perceived Cultural and Business Distance Decisions

The perceptions held by managers on different aspects of culture and business distance have an impact on global business, which turns out to be pivotal knowing the influence of the deemed cultural and business range between the company's local and international market countries. There were advantages as well as mitigating decisions that were made in the company that influenced the level of sustainability in the company. For the companies to meet most of their objectives and have a good performance in the market, they need good decisions. Competent judgments made by the public can be of a coherent process of making decisions. At every level of the company's structure, some individuals have different responsibilities to make decisions, which happen in

managerial positions. Multiple problems faced the company because of the globalization of the business. Some of the major problems facing Telkom company are stiff competition from other telecommunication operator companies, Rapid technological development globally, Liberalization of the telecommunication sector, High cost, and scarce frequency resources, privatization of the industry among other.

2. Globalization Challenges Facing Telkom Company

Some of the globalization challenges identified that are affecting the company are competition and drastic changes in the technology advancement from some of the other telecommunication operator companies in the region. These are the critical challenges that the company is trying to address. Other challenges are the quality of service, fall in revenues, loss of market shares and financial requirements to manage and run the business in distant countries with different cultural practices from those in the home country, and employee turnover rates.

3. Competition

The company is now faced and confronted by adverse challenges of its competitors who are also working day in day out to ensure that they are in the leading position. The ultimate number of telecommunication operator companies posing competition is not very strong, but the product line of each of the companies is stronger than one can imagine. Every telecommunication firm in Indonesia has differentiated each product line or brand to be relevant and appropriate with each of the targeted markets. This is where the ultimate level of competition comes from. This position is somewhat dependent on the value that is perceived by the customers, together with the price the company offers.

4. An Analysis of the Challenges Posed by Competitors

The primary companies posing stiff competition to Telkom Indonesia Company are GSM firms, Indosat, EL, and HCPT (Hutchison). These main brands have obtained and gained a position from the customers, but this respective position has been derogated within the last two to five years. The postpaid services are primarily positioned as flexible and considered high-end services since they are consumed by the people who are settled like the executives, bankers, businesspeople, and lecturers, among others. The prepaid services are generally in this case, and it is positioned in the center or middle. On the other hand, the prepaid is positioned for low-income individuals and teenagers, as the pricing for this service is more affordable and reliable. Both potentials, as well as existing competitors to Telkom Company, influence the company's profitability. Some competitors have taken different forms and have used in to preventing an influx into the market whenever benefits, adjusted the cost of capital expense costs. The most popular inhabitants that the company experiences from the competitors are economies of scale, such as in a case where the competitors benefit from bulk purchasing. While the company plans

to set up business in other countries, the company has always experienced the entry expenses, for example, costs of investment in technological advancements, and the distribution routes. The company has also experienced challenges related to the new legal authorities and the new laws, which tend to weaken the company's competitive position together with differentiation. Some of the companies offer substitute products that pose challenges to the company, whereby this threatens the country's profitability that relies entirely on the "relative-to-performance ratios of the different services," and commodities the companies offer to which customers go for to meet or fulfill the same essential needs. The bargaining power of customers is another challenge that is one of the two horizontal forces that impact the sponsoring of the appropriate value established by the company. The essential determinant aspect of buyer power is the customers' respective sizes and concentrations. Another factor related to the challenge of competition under the bargaining power degree where buyers are informed about the service and commodity the company offers and the ones competitors offer concerning the same product or service. The bargaining power of suppliers is another factor that competitors may pose to the company. This is a minor reflection of the ultimate bargaining power. The ability of the company to charge customers different pricing for particular services and products in line with the value established for each of the respective buyers normally depicts that the market is characterized by the high bargaining power the suppliers have and the low bargaining power of the buyers concerning the same thing with their competitor. However, Telkom Company has looked at the particular challenges affecting the company, and it has identified strengths and direction to handle each force.

5. Company Response to Challenges

In response to the competition issue, the company managers have decided on a strategy that considers multiple elements of competition, which comprise elements that reflect on the competences of the company. The first element the company managers considered in decision making is the intensity, and the other is quality. Intensity is a measure that puts together elements of the intensity of competition, the advantage of the costs, and the experience in the market. Quality is the measure that provides a reflection of the relative quality of products and the characteristics of the products. The decision made in tackling competition is the determination of cost-efficacy, product differentiation, focus, avoidance of competition by changing some products, and making adjustments in the services provided. The company has embraced the Ansoff Matrix Strategy, where it included four possible combinations, which are market penetration, product development, development of the market, and diversification. The company penetrated with its current products it had with the existing customers it had. The company then developed new products into the new markets it opened subsidiaries. Its entry to new geographical markets expands the market development strategy, where the company has grown significantly and expanded more in terms of market outreach. Telkom Company has managed to expand globally and meet most of

its objectives by countering the existing competition challenges posed through these strategies. The company also considered selling their shares to have many investors coming in the business to help in producing more products and gaining the competitive advantage.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, World globalization is a leading factor that leads companies to decide on international expansion with an objective to retain or grow the business. In light of making international marketing strategy decisions, where a company globalizes, the managers meet new challenges that are influenced by deemed cultural and geographic business range. Telkom Indonesia is a good example of companies that have been expanding their businesses internationally since 2007. However, the company has experienced challenges in expanding its business in new geographic locations. Some of the challenges posed are competition and adoption of the new business laws and regulations. The primary companies posing stiff competition to Telkom Indonesia Company are GSM firms, Indosat, EL, and HCPT (Hutchison). These main brands have obtained and gained a position from the customers, but this respective position has been derogated within the last two to five years. The challenges posed have been addressed competently and have resulted in positive results that are depicted by the success of the company in these different subsidiaries in different regions. However, we still have unanswered questions that need to be addressed in case of future research. Therefore, the company should assess the areas that experience challenges, and address these questions.

Figure 1. Telin-3 Data Centre Grand Opening

Source: <https://telegraf.co.id/setelah-diresmikan-data-center-telin-3->

Figure 2. Telin and Taisheng Collaboration 2019
 Source: <https://www.telin.net/id/company/newsroom>

Figure 3. Telkom Family Tree and Telin

Figure 4. Telkom and Telin Footprints Journey

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic “Globalization Enables Telkom Indonesia to be Interconnected with International Telecommunications Networks, Supporting Seamless Communication and Data Exchange Across Border”.

REFERENCES

- Azar, G. (2013). Managerial Perceptions of the Cultural Distance Basis for Internationalization Decisions by Firms. Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences.
- Benton, D. (2018). How Telkom Indonesia is transforming Indonesia into a Global Digital Hub. Technology.
- Carpenter, M. A. (2012). Challenges and Opportunities in International Business.
- Firmansyah, E. A. (2016). How can the Indonesian telecommunication giant persist amid the competition? a case of telkomsel INC. Research Gate.
- Hapsari, C. (2017). The Influence of Perceived Cultural and Business Distance on International Marketing Strategy Decisions; A Case Study of Telkom Indonesia International. International Review of Management and Marketing.
- Kipkurui, t. J. (2008). Strategic responses to increasing competitive challenges in the telecommunications industry in Kenya - a case of Telkom Kenya limited. University of Nairobi.
- Moon, T. (2011). The Effect of Cultural Distance on International Marketing Strategy: A Comparison of Cultural Distance and Managerial Perception Measures. Research Gate.
- Suryo, H. D. (2010). Report of Foreign Private Issuer Pursuant to Rule 13 A-16 Or 15d-16 Under the Securities Exchange Act of 1934. Washington.
- Utami, R. R. (2013). PT Telkom Part I: Company Overview. Belajar Branding.